

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D2.6

PARCopedia

WP 2 – T2.2

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Responsible author(s)	Isabella Apruzzese, BfR, isabella.apruzzese@bfr.bund.de Matthias Herzler, BfR, matthias.herzler@bfr.bund.de Sónia Namorado, INSA, sonia.namorado@insa.min-saude.pt Maria Rita Paiva Pessoa, INSA, rita.pessoa@insa.min-saude.pt
Co-authors	Denis Sarigiannis, AUTH, sarigiannis@auth.gr Giorgios Sarigiannis, AUTH, g.sarigiannis@hotmail.com Francois Busquet, CAAT Europe, francois.busquet@altertox.be Christina Tsitsimpikou, GCSL, x.tsitsimpikou@aade.gr Milena Horvat, JSI, milena.horvat@ijs.si Lukáš Pokorný, MU, lukas.pokorny@recetox.muni.cz Kateřina Šebková, MU, katerina.sebkova@recetox.muni.cz Pavla Lakdawala, MU, pavla.lakdawala@recetox.muni.cz Hanna Schulz, UBA, hanna.schulz@uba.de Liana Liebmann, UBA, liana.liebmann@uba.de Ralf Weber, UOB, r.j.weber@bham.ac.uk
Internal Reviewers	Magnus Løfstedt, EEA, magnus.lofstedt@eea.europa.eu Maria Uhl, EAA, maria.uhl@umweltbundesamt.at
External Reviewers	Suggested: Tamás Szigeti, NPHC, szigeti.tamas@nnk.gov.hu Ana Isabel Cañas Portilla, ISCIII, acanas@isciii.es
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¹ PU = Public

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1	2023-12-05	BfR	First draft
2	2023-12-15	BfR/INSA	Comments from WP2 leaders integrated
3	2024-01-22	BfR/INSA	Comments from PARC reviewers integrated, document updated with latest images

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Abstract

PARCopedia is a knowledge management and social media platform built under PARC for the community of professionals involved in chemical risk assessment (CRA), in Europe and beyond. The platform was launched on 15 November 2023, and it can be found at the URL: <https://www.parcopedia.eu/>.

PARCopedia consists of a WIKI component, which represents the knowledge base of the online platform; and of a social media component, which provides the opportunity for registered users to interact with each other. A dashboard is also provided at the beginning of the user experience to browse across different information and sections of the website quickly. A search engine is built to connect and search throughout *PARCopedia*'s different components.

PARCopedia targets CRA professionals in Europe and beyond, including many different actors across sectors and fields of expertise. Among other things, *PARCopedia* aims to overcome language and knowledge barriers that may hamper progress in CRA by providing a common platform where information is available and dialogues and exchange of ideas are possible and made easy.

Key Words

PARCopedia; knowledge management; chemical risk assessment; community platform; PARC; partnership; knowledge sharing

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Authors and Acknowledgements

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Abbreviations and acronyms

CRA	Chemical Risk Assessment
NAMs	New Approach Methodologies
PARC	Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

1. Introduction

PARC*opedia* is the knowledge management and community platform developed under PARC Task 2.2, “Knowledge management and uptake into policy”. It was launched on 15 November 2023, and all professionals of the chemical risk assessment (CRA) community can register to it: PARC*opedia* is open to individuals from both in and outside of PARC, including researchers, risk assessors, risk managers and policy makers that have a general understanding of the CRA processes, but who may have different ideas or points of view based on their different sectors, areas of work, and expertise.

PARC*opedia* intends to become the central online meeting place for PARC members as well as the larger CRA community. It will facilitate knowledge sharing and discussion on different topics of CRA and its innovation, thereby also fostering a broad and deep understanding of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) and their role in CRA.

The full conceptual basis of PARC*opedia* development is described in the PARC*opedia* scoping study, PARC deliverable D2.1, now available [online](#).

This document provides a description of the PARC*opedia* platform, which can be found online at <https://www.parcopedia.eu/>.

2. PARC*opedia*

The PARC*opedia* website consists of a dashboard including a search engine for queries across all elements of the platform, a knowledge base (“the WIKI”) and a social media component.

2.1. Dashboard

After logging in to PARC*opedia*, users start their experience by landing on the PARC*opedia* dashboard (*‘My Dashboard’*, Fig. 1). The page collects summarised information relevant for the CRA community, and it is continuously improved based on the needs of PARC*opedia* users.

- A header highlights editorials written by the PARC*opedia* team, or by any prominent volunteer within the community that expresses an interest to contribute.
- Below this header, announcements from the Editorial Team to all PARC*opedia* users are displayed, *inter alia* including tips on how to make the best use of the platform (e.g. *“Discover the group function on PARCopedia”*).
- Underneath the announcements section, a search bar allows to search all content across the different pages and sections of PARC*opedia*.
- Below the search bar, a set of hyperlinks provides quick access to commonly visited pages, i.e. “Profiles”, “Groups”, “Messages”, “Notifications”, “Calendar” and “Job Openings”.

Fig. 1: Screenshot of the upper part of the “My Dashboard” page on PARCopedia

- Further down, on the left-hand side of the page, a “Latest News” section is found. News items relevant to the CRA community are briefly summarised together with external links to the original websites (e.g. PARC website, ECHA, OECD, and other relevant sources). These news items are curated by the Editorial Team; however, users can also send suggestions for publication.
- To the right of the News section, a section on “Upcoming Events” provides an overview of conferences, webinars, trainings, workshops and other meetings of interest to the CRA community.
- Further down, on the bottom left of the page, internal links for popular and latest articles can be found (Fig. 2).
- At the bottom right of the dashboard, an activity stream with the latest platform activities from PARCopedia users is available. This *feed* can be filtered with respect to the information users wish to find (status updates, files shared, links shared, among other options).

Fig. 2: Screenshot of the lower part of the “My Dashboard” page on PARCopedia.

2.2. The WIKI

The *PARCopedia* WIKI is at the heart of *PARCopedia*, providing the knowledge base of the platform. It is the part of *PARCopedia* where the “official content” can be browsed, in the form of WIKI articles, which synthesise current knowledge on different topics and subtopics with relevant information for the CRA community, highlighting key elements and external sources, where appropriate. *PARCopedia* “official content” is subject to a quality-check process managed by the *PARCopedia* editorial team. This quality-check is purely editorial, and it aims to ensure consistency and readability of the articles. No peer-review process is otherwise in place in *PARCopedia*.

All users are encouraged to submit articles to the *PARCopedia* WIKI on any relevant topic in CRA within the existing topics and subtopics. Users who wish to contribute with an article on WIKI must submit a simple online form for initially expressing their interest to do so. The submission and revision process is summarised in the picture below.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the process to contribute to *PARCopedia* WIKI

In addition, contributions from experts in the field can also be directly requested by the Editorial Team (e.g. from the PARC’s Chemical and Methodology Leads). [A publishing guide](#) was developed by the *PARCopedia* editorial team to guide users and to define the processes through which different official content is uploaded to the platform.

PARCopedia’s WIKI is structured in six main categories, describing the main topics and areas of CRA (Chemicals, Methods, Regulatory, Institutions, Activities, Glossary), each one further sub-divided into different sub-categories (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4: Screenshot of the PARCopedia WIKI start page

A search engine is available to browse the WIKI, allowing for smart searches (e.g. truncated searches within all WIKI articles, Fig. 4).

Fig. 5: Screenshot of the WIKI search bar, with a truncated search being executed

Each article in the WIKI follows a specific structure, which differs based on the category (and often sub-category) it belongs to. This structure has been developed by PARCopedia's Editorial Team, in a template format, which is only shared with contributors by email. On the left-hand side of each article, users can find the table of contents, and on the right-hand side, the article's location within the WIKI.

Fig. 6: Partial screenshot of a PARCopedia WIKI page

Under each article, the contributors' information is shown by providing their name, link to PARCopedia profile and affiliation, thus acknowledging their contribution to that article. Revisions and regular updates of the articles are encouraged, also using the online form developed by the Editorial Team, in which case additional contributors will also be acknowledged at the bottom of the article.

All users are encouraged to leave comments under each article, ask questions or exchange points of view or ideas.

2.3. PARCopedia as a social media

2.3.1. Profiles

PARCopedia users can share information about themselves and their work, by creating a personal profile. Information that can be provided includes:

- a profile picture;
- job title and affiliation;
- a short biography;
- skills;
- links to other relevant personal pages outside of PARCopedia, including ResearchGate and LinkedIn.

In each personal profile, posts can be published, which can then be seen by users on the 'My Dashboard' page under 'Latest Activity'. The formats for posts include free text, photos, slideshows, quotes, files, videos, audios, links and polls.

Personal profiles can be set as public or private: public profiles can be seen by all PARCopedia registered users; private profiles can only be seen by the user's 'friends'.

PARCopedia also provides users with the possibility to contact other users or group members via private messages.

2.3.3. Groups

In *PARCopedia*, users can create and join existing groups (Fig. 6).

Fig. 7: Partial screenshot of a *PARCopedia* group page

The aim of this functionality is to share information or engage in focused discussions on specific topics. Groups allow users to add their thoughts in two main ways:

- by posting on the groups' general feed text, media, links, polls; and
- by creating discussion fora (Fig. 8) in a separate tab, to discuss and share on more specific topics.

Fig. 8: Partial screenshot of a *PARCopedia* group forum page

2.4. The search engine

The search engine, located at the top of the *My Dashboard* page (see Fig. 1 above), allows users to search across the whole platform of *PARCopedia* (the WIKI, the dashboard, the social media part). This search engine should not be confused with the one for searching the WIKI (see Fig. 5 above). While typing in a search string, a selection of matching search results is already displayed for quick access (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9: Screenshot of PARCopedia's search bar automatically displaying matching search results while the user is still typing in the search string

Using the "Advanced Search" function, the search can be filtered by page type (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10: Advanced Search filtered by page type

In addition, tags can be assigned to PARCopedia pages which then can be used to (further) filter the search, e.g. by CAS RN (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11: Advanced Search filtered by tag (CAS RN)

Search results are displayed on a new page (Fig. 12).

The screenshot shows a search interface with a search bar at the top. Below the search bar, there are filters for 'Any Post Type' and a search ID '228-250-8'. The search results are displayed under the heading 'Search results for: ""'. Two results are shown:

- New biomonitoring data on UV filters octocilene and 2-ethylhexyl salicylate in Germany**
In this new paper, a team from the German Institute for Prevention and Occupational Medicine of the German Social Accident Insurance (IPA) and the German Environment Agency (UBA) has published [...]
[Read more](#)
- Following RMOA by ANSES, ECHA publishes call for evidence for octocilene restriction**
In preparation of a restriction following a Risk Management Option Analysis (RMOA) by French PARC partner ANSES, ECHA has published a call for evidence for the substance octocilene (EC No. [...])
[Read more](#)

Fig. 12: Advanced Search result filtered by the CAS RN for the substance octocilene

3. PARCopedia community management

3.1. Registration to PARCopedia

Registration to PARCopedia is open to persons from both in- and outside of PARC. The target audience is the CRA community consisting of researchers, risk assessors, risk managers and policy makers with a general understanding of the CRA processes, bringing together professionals with different ideas and points of view, based on their sectors, areas of work, and expertise.

The registration process is conducted through a registration form (Fig. 13), which asks for the following information:

- PARCopedia username (mandatory)
- email address (mandatory)
- password (mandatory)
- full name (mandatory)
- institution name (mandatory)
- institution type (optional)
 - o academia (university or research organisation)
 - o government organisation (agency or ministry)
 - o industry
 - o international organisation
 - o non-governmental organisation
 - o other
- institution's affiliation to PARC
- institution's involvement in chemical risk assessment

The image displays two side-by-side screenshots of the PARCopedia registration form. The left screenshot shows the 'ACCOUNT DETAILS' section, which includes four required text input fields: 'Username', 'Email Address', 'Choose a Password', and 'Confirm Password'. Below these is the 'Profile Details' section, featuring two required text input fields: 'Name' and 'Institution Name'. Each of these fields has a visibility dropdown menu set to 'Everyone' and a 'Change' button. The right screenshot shows the 'Institution Location (city, country)' field, which is required and has a visibility dropdown set to 'My Friends'. Below this is the 'Institution type' section, which is required and contains five radio button options: 'Academia (university or research organisation)', 'Government organisation (agency or ministry)', 'Industry', 'International Organisation', 'Non-Governmental Organisation', and 'Other'. This section also has a visibility dropdown set to 'My Friends'. The next section asks 'Is your institution involved in PARC (as partner or affiliated entity)?' and is required, with a dropdown menu and a visibility dropdown set to 'My Friends'. The final section asks 'Is your institution involved in chemical risk assessment?' and is required, with a dropdown menu and a visibility dropdown set to 'My Friends'. At the bottom of the right screenshot, there is a disclaimer: 'By creating an account you agree to our Terms and Conditions and our Privacy Policy.' and two buttons: a blue 'REGISTER' button and a green 'LOG IN' button.

Fig. 13: Screenshots of the registration form for PARCopedia

Upon registration, users agree to the terms and conditions, as well as to the privacy policy of PARCopedia. The registration form of PARCopedia can be seen at: <https://www.parcopedia.eu/register/>.

3.2. Members' directory

All registered users can be found in the *PARCopedia* members' directory (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14: Screenshots of the *PARCopedia* members' directory

3.3. Rules and rights

A footer (Fig. 15) with the following links, is available on all *PARCopedia* pages and is also accessible for non-registered users from the *PARCopedia* welcome page:

- Contacts
- Acknowledgements
- Terms and Conditions
- Code of Conduct
- Privacy Policy
- Cookie Policy

Fig. 15: Screenshot of the *PARCopedia* footer

References

- *PARCopedia* online:
<https://www.parcopedia.eu>
- *PARCopedia* scoping study:
https://www.eu-parc.eu/sites/default/files/2023-06/PARC_D2.2.pdf